

Investors' Awareness Towards Gold Monetization Scheme

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S.Barath Raj

I M.Com Bank Management

M.Swetha

II M.Com Bank Management

KRMMC, Adyar, Chennai

Introduction

Gold has a deep-rooted significance in Indian history, alluring people with its beauty, charm, and as a sign of wealth. The mindset of Indians investing in gold has increased some time. This may be due to cultural significance, sentimental values, and appreciations in the value of gold. Gold is considered as an auspicious symbol of wealth. Gold monetization scheme was launched on 5th November 2015 by the Prime Minister of India Mr. Narendra Modi to bring out the idle gold from the households and organization. Gold monetization scheme provides an opportunity for individuals to make a profit from the old jewelry lying in bank lockers and safety boxes. This scheme is useful for both government and gold holders, as the gold deposit account holders can earn interest from the idle assets lying either in their houses or in safety lockers. As far as, the Government of India is concerned, this scheme enables the government to reduce the import of gold.

Objectives

This research paper attempts to explore the awareness level of investors towards gold monetization scheme. An overview of gold monetization scheme is presented, and suggestions are offered to promote gold monetization scheme amongst the investors.

Methodology

The study is based on primary and secondary data. The primary data is collected from 100 respondents and secondary data is taken through websites, journals and, magazines.

An Overview of Gold Monetization Scheme

Gold Monetization Scheme (GMS) is the modification of 'Gold Deposit Scheme' (GDS) and 'Gold Metal Loan Scheme (GML). The scheme was introduced to mobilize idle gold held by individuals and institutions of our country. It will help to reduce import of gold by our Government.

Gold Deposit Account- A gold deposit account has to be opened with the designated bank for depositing gold under Gold Monetization Scheme. All the Scheduled Commercial Banks excluding RRBs will be eligible to implement the Scheme. The opening of gold deposit accounts will be subject to the same rules with regard to customer identification as are applied to any other deposit account. The customer should hold Savings / Current Account with a Bank before opening Gold deposit account for the credit of interest on the gold deposit.

Eligibility - This scheme is open to resident Indians, Hindu Undivided Families, Partnership firms, Proprietorship, Companies and Charitable institutions. It is also open to Central Government, State Government or Government - owned organizations.

Collection and Purity Testing Center (CPTC) – Gold shall be deposited at collection and purity testing center which are certified by the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS). The purity of the gold deposited will be assessed, and certificate will be issued after testing the purity.

Acceptance of deposits - The minimum deposit of the gold under GMS at any one time shall be 30 grams of raw gold (bars, coins, jewelry excluding stones and other metals). There is no maximum limit for depositing gold under gold monetization scheme.

Short Term Bank Deposit (STBD) - Gold can be deposited under the GMS with a designated bank for a short term period of 1-3 years.

Medium and long term government deposit (MLTGD) - Medium term deposit can be made for a period ranging for 5 to 7 years, and the long term deposits can be made for a period ranging from 12 to 15 years or for such a period decided by the central government.

Interest Rates- The designated banks are free to fix the interest rates on these deposits. The interest shall be credited in the deposit accounts on the respective due dates and will be with drawable periodically or at maturity as per the terms of the deposit. The current rates of interest as notified by the Central Government are as under:

- (i) On medium - term deposit – 2.25% p.a.
- (ii) On long term- deposit – 2.50% p.a.

Benefits to Investors

1. Depositors in gold monetization scheme can earn interest on idle gold.
2. The scheme offers flexibility and, the investors can withdraw the investment when required.
3. Choice is given to the gold depositor to redeem in the form of cash or gold. However that the gold depositor needs to state the redemption preference at the time of gold deposit.
4. It helps to eliminate locker rent but at the same time provides safe maintenance of gold.
5. The earning on gold monetization scheme is exempted from capital gain tax, wealth tax and income tax.

Analysis And Interpretation

Gender Distribution

Gender	No.of Respondents	Percentage
Male	60	60
Female	40	40
Total	100	100

It is inferred from the above table, 60% of the respondents were male, and 40% of the respondents were female.

Age Distribution

15% of the respondents were between the age group of 25 – 35years, 38% of the respondents were between 35 – 45 years, 16% of the respondents were between 45 – 55 years, 10% were below 25 years, and 21% were above 55 years.

Qualification

37% of the respondents were professionals, 29% were under graduates, 23% were post graduates, and 11% of the respondents did not have collegiate education.

Income Distribution

Majority of the respondents (40%) were within the monthly income of Rs. 25,000 – Rs. 50,000, and 30% of the respondents were within the monthly income of Rs. 50,000 – Rs. 75,000. 20% of the respondent were earning below Rs.25, 000. 8% of the respondent were earning income between Rs.75, 000 – Rs.1, 00,000 and 2% of the respondents earn income above Rs. 1, 00,000.

Frequency of Investment

Majority of the respondents (48%) saved income through the purchase of gold annually, 32% of the respondent saved monthly, 12% of the respondent saved quarterly, and remaining 8% saved half-yearly in gold.

Mode of Investment in Gold

50% of the respondent invested in jewelry, 40% invested in the form of bars and coins and, 10% in the form of E-Gold.

Awareness on Gold Monetization Scheme

30% of the respondents were aware of gold monetization scheme, 60% of the respondents were not aware of gold monetization scheme and, 10% remained neutral concerning awareness level of gold monetization scheme.

Minimum Investment in GMS

Majority of the respondents (47%) were not aware of the minimum investment that shall be made in gold monetization scheme. 31% of the respondent stated that 30 grams, 12% stated 90 grams, and 10% stated 120 grams as the minimum level of investment in gold monetization scheme.

Benefits of Gold Monetization Scheme

Majority of the respondents (48%) felt gold monetization scheme helps to earn interest on idle gold, 36% of the respondents felt it was safe to maintain gold in gold, monetization scheme. Avoidance of safety locker rent was the next reason for choosing gold monetization scheme.

Factors that Demotivate in Investment in Gold

Dislike in the conversion of gold (43%) was the major reason that demotivated the respondents from investing in gold monetization scheme. Respondents stated that they did not have awareness (40%) about GMS. The next reason stated was a lower rate of interest (12%) that was offered on gold monetization scheme. Fear of tax with 5% was the least factor that demotivated the respondents.

Suggestions

- The Central government and commercial banks must create awareness about gold monetization scheme to the customers and, the investors
- Transparency must be introduced in the process of conversion of gold, and it is better to standardize the gold bar that is produced during the process.
- The return offered by banks as interest can be enhanced to attract depositors.
- CPTC can be more customers friendly to attract uneducated investors.
- An option to redeem on Akshaya Tritiya or festivals time can promote more investors to invest in gold monetization scheme
- Financial literacy programs can be organized to overcome the fear of tax that exists in the mind of investors.

Conclusion

Gold monetization scheme is very novel scheme can help to mobilize idle gold and thereby can help in the reduction of gold imports.

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